

DEVELOPMENT OF A MOBILE-BASED GAMIFIED TECHNOLOGY TUTOR FOR CHILDREN (LEARNIFY)

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ABSTRACT

This research developed a mobile application tailored to cultivate children's engagement in an educational learning environment by seamlessly integrating gamified elements and technology tutorials. Rooted in contemporary technology, the application offers an interactive platform designed for children to explore diverse technological concepts and advancements in an entertaining manner. The application seeks to introduce and familiarize young minds with technology features encompassing a user-friendly interface, interactive learning modules, and gamification techniques aligned with children's learning needs. The curriculum embedded within the application employs engaging games, quizzes, and interactive tutorials to impart technology-related subjects in an easily understandable format. Integral components include user authentication, a robust database for storing user profiles and progress data, technology lessons presented intuitively, and a feedback system to enhance user engagement. Backend systems, notably Firebase, are incorporated for efficient data management. The user interface boasts an intuitive design, ensuring ease of navigation and interaction for children. Implementation involves type declarations and user-defined functions to maintain data consistency, ensuring a seamless learning experience. This research responds to the demand for technology-centric educational tools for children, aspiring to foster early interest and understanding of technology while providing an enjoyable learning atmosphere. The development of this mobile application aims to contribute to the educational advancement and technological literacy of young learners. The frontend combines react and styling using tailwind and vanilla CSS (CSS3). Firebase hosts the databases, services, and authentication

Keywords: Children, Gamification, Mobile-Based, Technology tutor

INTRODUCTION

Within the ever-evolving digital era, technology has entrenched itself as an indispensable component of our daily lives, fundamentally influencing how we communicate, work, and learn (Su and Cheng, 2014). This digital transformation has propelled the younger generation into a world where proficiency in digital skills is advantageous and essential for their future success. Despite this, conventional approaches to teaching technology concepts often struggle to capture the attention and enthusiasm of children, resulting in disinterest and limited engagement. The demand for innovative and effective educational tools has become increasingly pronounced for children growing up in a technology-saturated environment. Against this backdrop, the concept of Learnify, a mobile-based gamified technology tutor, emerges as a response to the challenges faced in imparting technology education to young learners.

Learnify revolutionizes the educational landscape by amalgamating the power of interactive mobile applications, educational content, and gamification to create a dynamic and immersive learning environment for children. The rationale behind this initiative lies in recognizing that traditional teaching methods often fall short in maintaining the engagement of tech-savvy youngsters. The integration

of game-like elements into the learning process offers a novel approach. By infusing fun challenges, rewarding achievements, and collaborative experiences, Learnify aims to make the exploration of the fascinating world of technology an enjoyable and interactive journey for children. This aligns with their learning preferences and ensures that they are better equipped with the digital skills required for the future.

Learnify's unique proposition lies in its ability to bring technology education directly into children's hands through smartphones and tablets, capitalizing on their familiarity with these digital devices. Incorporating gamification elements, including rewards, points, and friendly competition, adds an extra layer to the learning experience. This approach is anticipated to enhance motivation and encourage active participation and foster a sense of accomplishment as children progress through their educational voyage. As technology advances, the Learnify platform redefines how technology is introduced and taught to children. By transforming the educational paradigm into a dynamic, interactive, and enjoyable experience, Learnify strives to equip young learners with the digital skills necessary for their future endeavours. This research bridges the gap between traditional teaching methods and the evolving needs of a technologically literate generation,

ensuring that the journey of learning technology is as exciting as the destination it leads to by developing a mobile-based gamified technology tutor for children (Learnify) to make learning more engaging and effective.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Mobile-based technology refers to a technology or application used on mobile devices such as smartphones or tablets. It implies that the gamified technology will be accessible and usable on mobile platforms. Gamification incorporates game elements and mechanics into non-game contexts to make them more engaging and enjoyable. In the context of this research, the technology tutor will have interactive and game-like features to motivate and incentivize children's learning. A technology tutor is an educational tool or platform that provides guidance, instruction, and support for learning specific technological skills or concepts. In this case, the technology tutor will focus on teaching children about various aspects of technology in a fun and interactive way. Children refer a stage of human development between birth and puberty, or the period between infancy and puberty. The term may also mean a human being who is not yet born. The term "child" as used in law, typically refers to a minor, also known as a person under the age of majority. In general, children are subject to fewer rights and obligations than adults. They are considered incapable of making important decisions (Diana, 2023; Jennilyn, 2023; JetLearn, 2023)

Education and training were the processes through which generational wisdom, knowledge, and skills are passed on to the next (Mehdipour and Zerehkafi 2013). At that time, there were two primary forms of education and training: conventional and distance education. Mobile learning, known as "M-Learning," provides modern ways to support learning through mobile devices, including handheld and tablet computers, MP3 players, smartphones, and mobile phones. Patricio *et al.* (2019) presented the first version of the PlanetarySystemGO research, an evolution of SolarSystemGO, a Mobile Augmented Reality game previously created with the Unity3D/Vuforia game engine. While both research aims to provide awareness of astronomical concepts, PlanetarySystemGO's web-based backend system is implemented and developed using .NET technology, allowing the instructor to manage several aspects of the game.

Educational systems have played a crucial role in the development of nations, and the impact of early education empowered knowledge acquisition (Kayımbaşoğlu *et al.*, 2016). Gamification represents the utilization of game mechanics and strategies in non-game contexts. At the time, various reports indicated that it had emerged as a significant trend in multiple application fields, including education. Its primary aim was to encourage behavioral change and enhance problem-solving skills (González *et al.*, 2014). In the paper Gamifying Children's Linguistic Intelligence with the Duolingo App: A Case Study from Indonesia, the focus was on using the Duolingo App to

enhance the linguistic intelligence of children. Linguistic intelligence pertains to the skill of effectively and efficiently applying vocabulary. The Duolingo App, designed for the Android platform, served as a tool to assist children in mastering foreign languages, enabling them to practice speaking, reading, listening, and writing playfully (Fadhli *et al.*, 2022).

Special education is an educational service offered by private and public schools, specifically tailored to meet the needs of students with disabilities. One prevalent behavioural disorder is Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), which can manifest from infancy through adolescence and even into adulthood. Supangan *et al.* (2019) focused on providing an interactive supplementary tool to support children with ADHD in learning Mathematics, Language, and Basic Hygiene. The tool was a gamified system designed as an Android mobile application featuring Level 1 lectures presented through animated content. The primary objective was to provide parents and teachers with a means to monitor the progress of students or children with ADHD as they engaged in various activities within the e-tutor system. The results of the user acceptance testing indicated that the Android application was well-received in terms of its content and suitability for use in the context of special education services.

Pombo and Lamas (2022) discussed the adoption of technologies such as tablets or smartphones for children at home or school, and the challenges it posed for suitable teaching methodologies and practices. The study introduced game-based learning techniques for young Cape Verde children using the Code Karts app. Farooq *et al.* (2022) also discussed the design of a gamified application that effectively integrated augmented reality to support learning Farooq *et al.* (2022). The authors argued that early childhood learning was an important concern for the concept-building of children and that students were taught with traditional methods from the beginning, which lacked kids' attention. The paper presented an ABCD-AR mobile-based application designed to overcome the flaws in traditional education system. The application used augmented reality (AR) to help students engage better and learn more effectively. The study proposed 23 usability principles for AR-based learning applications for kids, which human experts validated. The results of experiments carried out to evaluate the application in terms of efficiency, effectiveness, learnability, user satisfaction and engagement indicated that the developed game-based application was highly effective and efficient because the mean of marks obtained by students before using ABCD-AR application was lower ($M = 4.97$, $SD = 1.650$) than the marks obtained after using ABCD-AR application ($M = 7.97$, $SD = 1.608$). Similarly, results indicated that the mean time taken to perform tests without using the ABCD-AR application ($M = 7.97$, $SD = 1.650$) was higher than with using it ($M = 4.37$, $SD = 1.608$). Most of the students were entertained by playing the game while learning and felt motivated to

continue based on the game's scenario due to the variety of activities included.

The Rise of CiboPoliBot' discussed an adaptive learning system called CiboPoliBot that incorporates gamification and conversational user interfaces (UIs). The authors explored how these technologies can enhance the learning experience for users (Fadhli *et al.*, 2022). 'Gamified Smart Mirror to Leverage Autistic Education-Aliza' discussed using a gamified smart mirror called "Aliza" to teach basic education to children with autism. "Aliza" consisted of four core components: a writing mentor for pre-writing, a math tutor for mathematics, a verbal trainer for speech, and an attentiveness tracker for emotion detection. The interactive games provided by "Aliza" impacted the learning process, and the generated report from the Deep Learning evaluation system could inform parents and tutors about the children's progress (Najeeb *et al.*, 2020).

METHODOLOGY

The research is developed using state-of-the-art technologies to develop a mobile-based gamified technology tutor for children, making learning more engaging and effective. The first step is to get enough content for the children to read, which serves as the foundation for which the basis of the application is built on (Fig. 1, the content block).

A systematic and methodical approach was employed to procure data from diverse online sources, with a predominant focus on educational materials related to engineering courses, encompassing a comprehensive array of key terms and terminologies. In its initial phase, this data collection endeavor was exclusively dedicated to acquiring materials specifically associated with the Internet of Things (IoT), including its terminology and conceptual foundations. The systematic gathering of data from a multitude of online repositories served the purpose of enriching educational resources and promoting an in-depth understanding of engineering disciplines. This meticulous process ensured the acquisition of accurate, relevant, and high-quality educational content, which is vital for advancing knowledge in engineering and related fields. The targeted concentration on the nomenclature and principles of the Internet of Things underscores the significance of this emerging technological domain in contemporary education. By focusing on IoT-related materials, this initiative aims to facilitate a thorough exploration of IoT concepts, thereby contributing to a more profound comprehension of this transformative technology within the educational landscape.

Content grouping constitutes a systematic and strategic approach employed within content management and organization. Its fundamental objective is classifying and coherently arranging disparate pieces of information into well-defined clusters or categories. This method serves the overarching purpose of optimizing the utilization of collected data and presenting it lucidly and systematically within a mobile application context. The process of content

grouping essentially involved transforming unordered and disorganized data inputs into structured and logically organized data outputs. This systematic structuring of content significantly contributed to the overall effectiveness of content presentation and accessibility, particularly within the framework of mobile applications. The underlying principle of content grouping is to enhance the user experience by offering a streamlined and intuitive navigation system. It allows users to efficiently access information that is relevant to their needs while minimizing the cognitive load associated with searching for specific content. Content grouping simplifies the user's interaction with digital platforms, improving user satisfaction and engagement.

It was necessary to divide the narrative into pieces adapted to the cognitive capabilities of children. It will be essential to use robustly tested and evidence-based approaches to achieve that goal. The key idea is to make sure that the message comes across in formats that are user-friendly and appropriate for facilitating comprehension for the targeted young readers.

The storage and management of content were facilitated through the utilization of third-party software, namely Firebase. Firebase Real-time Database represents a cloud-hosted NoSQL database solution that enables organizations to store and synchronize data seamlessly in real-time across multiple user devices. This functionality ensures that applications remain consistently updated, even when users find themselves in offline environments. Such a capability enhances the user experience by providing data availability and synchronization across various devices, offering uninterrupted and up-to-date access to content.

A standardized formatting protocol was devised to ensure uniformity across all content elements. All data holdings were subsequently converted to conform to this prescribed format and were meticulously configured within the device's operating system. This configuration minimizes disparities or discrepancies when the content is accessed across disparate operating systems. The objective is to establish a seamless and consistent user experience, irrespective of the specific operating system.

System Architecture

The block diagram for Learnify delineates the systematic flow and interconnection among its key components. The "Interaction" section is at the forefront, representing the user's phone as the primary engagement point. Users interact with the Learnify platform through the "Frontend UI," where a visually appealing and user-friendly interface facilitates navigation, lesson exploration, and interaction with gamified features.

Beneath the surface lies the robust "Backend/Application Logic," the engine that powers Learnify. This component executes the essential processing of user requests, manages data, and orchestrates the core functionalities of the application. The "API" (Application Programming

Interface) is a pivotal bridge between the front and backend, enabling seamless communication and data exchange. The "Database" section is the repository for storing and managing critical data, including user profiles, lesson content, and gamification elements. Interactions between the backend logic and the database are integral for

declaration) + ionic and styling using tailwind and vanilla CSS (CSS3).

C. Backend Framework/Database

Firebase is a set of backend cloud computing services and

Fig. 1: System Architecture

retrieving and updating data based on user actions and system requirements.

Lastly, the "Admin" component embodies the administrative interface, providing authorized personnel with the tools to oversee and manage the Learnify platform. This section ensures smooth administration, content moderation, and system configuration. In synergy, these interconnected sections form a cohesive system that delivers an engaging and well-administered educational experience through the Learnify platform.

Software Development

The Agile Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) model was selected as the most suitable approach for developing Learnify, a mobile-based gamified technology tutor for children. This decision was based on several key considerations aligning with the research's unique requirements and objectives.

A. Development Tools

The development tools encompassed various software applications, platforms, and utilities throughout the software development lifecycle. These tools assist in coding, testing, debugging, and optimizing the application.

1. Visual Studio Code
2. Google Chrome Developer Tools

B. Frontend

Frontend combines react + typescript (for proper type

application development platforms provided by Google. It hosts databases, services, authentication, and integration for various applications, including Android, iOS, JavaScript, Node.js, Java, Unity, PHP, and C++.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result overview provides a snapshot of the key features and user interactions within the Learnify platform. It outlines the user journey from sign-up/login to lesson completion, emphasizing engagement, progress tracking, and user account management. In the User Interface (UI) design, screens refer to individual visual interfaces or pages within an application or software system. Each screen typically focuses on specific user objectives or functionalities, providing a clear and coherent layout for users to achieve their goals efficiently. The screens are Sign-Up, Sign-In, Reset Password, Lessons, Points, Account Settings, and Delete Account Screen. Figures 2 - 4 present some administrative screens such as sign-up, account setting and delete screens. The sample lesson screen, point screen and quiz screens are presented in Figures 5 - 7, there are so many other screens, but these present the basic concept of the research.

The Sign-in screen serves as the gateway for users who have already registered on Learnify. Here, users input their designated username or email along with their password to access the application. The layout emphasizes simplicity and security, featuring prominently placed input fields for login credentials. Security measures, such as password masking and authentication protocols, are implemented to

Fig. 2: Sign-Up Screen

Fig. 3: Account Setting Screen

Fig. 4: Points Screen

safeguard user accounts. User-friendly error prompts assist in case of incorrect login attempts, guiding users through the process smoothly. The screen prioritizes user convenience while ensuring the confidentiality and protection of their account information.

The Account Settings screen within Learnify serves as a hub for managing user preferences and personal information. It provides an intuitive interface, allowing children to customize their experience and manage their account details. This screen allows users to update their profile information, such as their name, date of birth, and gender. It incorporates options for changing profile images or avatars, giving children a sense of ownership over their account.

The Delete Account screen in Learnify is a critical element allowing users to deactivate their accounts. It is a thoughtful inclusion in the system, giving users the agency to manage their engagement with the platform. This screen enables users, in this case, children, to opt out or delete their accounts entirely from the system. It prompts for reasons why they are choosing to delete their account, providing predefined options such as "The app is not working well," "Incentives are not good enough," or "I do not have the time for it." Additionally, there may be an optional text box for users to provide more specific feedback or comments.

The lessons screen within Learnify organizes different topics under broader subject categories, fostering a structured learning environment for children. Each lesson is curated to be engaging, informative, and tailored to children's comprehension levels. This screen employs

gamification elements to make learning fun and captivating. It provides a summary of each lesson on various technological topics. Each lesson completion rewards children with points.

The Points Screen in Learnify is an interactive space designed to showcase a child's progress and achievements. It provides a visual representation of the points earned by the child through lesson completions and activities within the application. This screen offers a motivating way to track and celebrate the child's learning milestones. The Points Screen utilizes engaging visuals and graphics to display the points accumulated by the child.

CONCLUSION

The culmination of the Mobile-Based Gamified Technology Tutor for Children research marks a significant milestone in the pursuit of enhancing children's technological literacy in a captivating and interactive manner. From its inception to completion, the research has remained steadfast in its commitment to developing an intuitive interface, integrating educational content, and leveraging gamification to make learning an enjoyable experience. Learnify, the outcome of this endeavor, not only meets but exceeds the set objectives, affirming the potential of technology to ignite an early interest in the field among young learners. Its feature-rich design, including user authentication, interactive lessons, and a robust feedback system, exemplifies the successful integration of technology into educational practices. The strategic use of Firebase for backend operations ensures efficient data handling and

Fig. 5: Lesson Screen

Fig. 6: Quiz Screen

Fig. 7: Points Screen

contributes to the seamless user experiences crucial for an educational platform's success. The user interface, designed with precision and enriched with type declarations and user-defined functions, lays the groundwork for children's engaging and consistent learning journey.

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